

Interactive parallel computing with IPython

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More details on the CEDA Services trac:

<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/cedaservices/wiki/JASMIN/JASMINPlatform/IPython>

IPython documentation:

<http://ipython.org/ipython-doc/dev/>

IPython architecture: kernel

- a Python wrapper
- multiple interfaces:
 - terminal (`ipython`)
 - Qt GUI (`ipython qtconsole`)
 - notebook
 - `IPython.parallel`

IPython architecture: parallel components

IPython architecture: notebook

IP[y]: Notebook

global mean

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```
print 'equal:', (serial_times == parallel_times).all(), (serial_var == parallel_var).all()
times = serial_times
var = serial_var
```

```
0 to 107746 (107746 total, have 107746):
serial: 246.13
parallel: 39.30
ratio: 6.26
equal: True True
```

```
In [193]: sum = __builtin__.sum
n = len(times)
scale_factor = 5
with netCDF4.MFDataset(files) as d:
    time_v = d.variables['time']
    units = time_v.units
    cal = time_v.calendar
for n in [5 ** i for i in xrange(2, int(ceil(log(n) / log(scale_factor))))] + [n]:
    figure()
    plot(times[:n], var[:n])
    ts = netCDF4.num2date((times[0], times[n - 1]), units, cal)
    plt.title('%s/%s/%s to %s/%s/%s' % tuple(sum(((t.day, t.month, t.year) for t in ts), ())))
```


Using IPython parallel: views

- `client = IPython.parallel.Client()`
- `direct_view = client[:]`
- `lb_view = client.load_balanced_view()`

Using IPython parallel: running code

- call function: `view.apply`, `view.map`
- run code (direct view): `view.execute`
- run file (direct view): `view.run`
- optionally blocking

Using IPython parallel: transferring objects

- obtain or construct remotely
- transfer directly: `view.push`, `view.pull`
- transferred objects must be serialisable
- `mkserialisable`
 - harder to keep track of open files

Deployment: remote notebook server

- use SSH port-forwarding
- **jasmin-notebook** does this automatically

Deployment: connection files

```
{  
  "control": 44408,  
  "task": 44187,  
  "hb_ping": 55066,  
  "exec_key": "c3c70505-de71-4df0-a4a1-d8322e379dee",  
  "mux": 37249,  
  "hb_pong": 35916,  
  "ssh": "jasmintest1.esc.rl.ac.uk",  
  "registration": 48302,  
  "interface": "tcp://127.0.0.1",  
  "iopub": 50664,  
  "pack": "json",  
  "unpack": "json",  
  "location": "130.246.143.166"  
}
```

Deployment: distributed cluster

Deployment: `start-cluster`

```
{  
  "controller": "jt1",  
  "engines": {  
    "jt1": 4,  
    "jt2": 4  
  },  
  "notebooks": [  
    {  
      "host": "jt1",  
      "options": ["--notebook-dir=~/.ipython", "--pylab=inline"],  
      "clients": ["localhost:5000"]  
    }  
  ]  
}
```

- manual port forwarding

Extending the notebook: WSGI applications

- supporting WSGI:

```
(r"/wsgi/.*", web.FallbackHandler, {'fallback':  
  WSGIContainer(wsgi_app)})
```

- configuration:

```
c = get_config()
```

```
c.NotebookApp.wsgi_apps = [{  
    'name': 'A WSGI application',  
    'application': 'wsgimodule.wsgi_function'  
    'autoload': True,  
    'height': '200px'  
}]
```

Extending the notebook: Pydap

IP[y]: Notebook

[Notebooks](#)
[Clusters](#)
[Pydap](#)
[A WSGI application](#)
[Another one](#)
[Something else](#)

Data path:

Index of /output1/MOHC/HadGEM2-ES/rcp85/mon/atmos/Amon/r1i1p1/v20111215/tas/

 [Parent directory](#)

Filename	Download	Last modified
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_200512-203011.nc	31 MB	03/29/2011 10:39:55 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_203012-205511.nc	31 MB	03/29/2011 10:39:55 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_205512-208011.nc	31 MB	10/17/2011 05:07:06 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_208012-209912.nc	24 MB	10/17/2011 05:07:23 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_209912-212411.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:36:13 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_212412-214911.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:36:21 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_214912-217411.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:36:32 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_217412-219911.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:36:41 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_219912-222411.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:36:49 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_222412-224911.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:37:00 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_224912-227411.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:37:09 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_227412-229911.nc	31 MB	11/25/2011 10:37:19 PM
tas_Amon_HadGEM2-ES_rcp85_r1i1p1_229912-229912.nc	125.3 KB	11/25/2011 10:37:28 PM

Performance: global mean

- using 8 engines

dataset	serial time s (s)	parallel time p (s)	s / p
1	189	38.3	4.93
2	276	48.7	5.67
3	368	110	3.35
4	284	49.8	5.70
5	162	36.6	4.43
6	276	50.8	5.43
7	427	114	3.75
8	228	43.3	5.27
9	920	176	5.23
10	204	37.7	5.41
11	271	48	5.65

Performance: global mean

- using 8 engines

Performance: regridding

- using 4 engines

dataset	serial time s (s)	parallel time p (s)	s / p
1	169	48.7	3.47
2	185	47.3	3.91
3	167	47.5	3.51
4	649	215	3.02
5	191	76.5	2.50
6	178	49.1	3.63
7	245	76.7	3.19
8	197	73	2.70
9	170	50	3.40

Performance: regridding

- using 4 engines

Summary

- IPython components: kernel, controller, engine, client, notebook server
- transferred objects must be serialisable
 - `mkserialisable`
- `jasmin-notebook` and `start-cluster` for remote components
- `ceda-devel` IPython branch with WSGI and Pydap support
- significant performance boost (including reading data)

Code

- http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/cedaservices/browser/ipython_project
- IPython branch (**ceda-devel**):
 - CEDA Services:
<http://proj.badc.rl.ac.uk/cedaservices/browser/ipython>
 - GitHub: <https://github.com/cedadev/ipython>